

1 **Transcriptional targets of the retinoblastoma tumor suppressor (*Rb1*).**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 East Islip, NY USA 11730
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 The retinoblastoma tumor suppressor (*Rb1*) exists, in a hypophosphorylated state, bound to the E2F
6 family of transcription factors in the cytoplasm. Upon phosphorylation by the cyclin dependent kinases
7 CDK4/6, hyper phosphorylated *Rb1* is liberated (inactivated) from E2F binding, at which time E2Fs
8 translocate to the nucleus and activate expression of genes important for cell cycle progression. Likewise,
9 *Rb1* activation during tumor suppression results in induction and repression of a discrete network of genes
10 whose identity and characteristic remain to be completely defined. We utilized whole transcriptome
11 technologies to blindly identify genes controlled by *Rb1* tumor suppression. We describe here
12 identification of the TNF superfamily gene member, the caspase-8 and FADD-like apoptosis regulator
13 *CFLAR* and nuclear transcription factor Y subunit alpha *NFYA* as genes whose induction defines tumor
14 suppression by *Rb1*.
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Results

We measured total transcription in three human cellular systems, MCF7, IMR90, and human embryonic stem cells, in which *Rb1* deletion was engineered. To combine loss- and gain-of-function approaches, we also measured total transcription in SAOS human osteosarcoma cells with ectopic expression of *Rb1*.

Figure 1: Identification of the TNF superfamily survival gene CFLAR as a target of the Rb1 tumor suppression program.

1a. GSE199919: Rb1 -/- MCF7

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8837	1.61E-02	0.184	2.406606	0.4421753	748.27	CFLAR	6066/16815	63.9

1b. GSE22842: SAOS expressing Rb1

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
235427_at	2.59E-03	-4.0896296	-1.320558	-0.49553583	CFLAR	883/54675	98.4

1c. GSE173127: RB1 -/- IMR90

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8837	2.93E-01	0.1143	-1.0525337	-1.20E-01	2671.43	CFLAR	5157/18019	71.5

1d. GSE84504: Rb1-/- hES

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
8837	7.16E-04	0.331	3.3834793	1.12	558.57	CFLAR	33/18814	99.8

Figure 2: Identification of the transcription factor NFYA as a target of the Rb1 tumor suppression program.

2a. GSE199919: Rb1 -/- MCF7

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4800	5.36E-03	0.137	-2.784559	-0.3818827	901.01	NFYA	4923/16815	70.7

2b. GSE22842: SAOS expressing Rb1

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
204107_at	1.16E-01	-1.7359383	-4.925765	-0.49699417	NFYA	9985/54675	81.7

2c. GSE173127: RB1 -/- IMR90

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMea	Gene	Rank	%DE
4800	8.01E-02	0.1203	1.7500738	2.11E-01	1748.49	NFYA	2126/18019	88.2

2d. GSE84504: Rb1-/- hES

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
4800	6.93E-01	0.432	0.3953166	1.71E-01	980.1	NFYA	4483/18814	76.2

Loss of Rb1 resulted in loss of CFLAR expression, while Rb1 expression resulted in CFLAR induction, save for IMR90 cells, where Rb1 loss resulted in CFLAR induction (Figure 1). Similarly, loss of Rb1 resulted in loss of NFYA expression, while expression of Rb1 resulted in NFYA induction, save for MCF7, where Rb1 loss resulted in NFYA induction (Figure 2).

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Discussion

We described here the identification of CFLAR and NFYA as transcriptional targets of the Rb1 tumor suppression program. We are currently using whole transcriptome approaches to more comprehensively define the scope of *Rb1* transcriptional targets (manuscript in preparation).

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Methods

We utilized whole transcriptome technologies: RNA-sequencing and microarray-based (published; see above) measurement of total transcription in conjunction with R-based computational methods to blindly extract gene expression targets of Rb1 suppression in human cells integrating gain- and loss-of-function approaches.